

UNDERSTANDING OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: This work analyses about definition and meaning of intercultural communication and gives general information about this communication. This article also includes information about the terms of culture, communication, Multiculturalism, interpersonal communication. Intercultural Communication means information from many social groups, including those with various educational, social, ethnic, and religious origins, is shared through intercultural dialogue. It aims to comprehend the variations in behavior, communication, and worldview among individuals from various cultural backgrounds.

Key words: Intercultural Communication, culture, communication, Multiculturalism, interpersonal communication

The study of intercultural communication focuses on how people communicate across cultural and social boundaries, or how culture affects communication. It addresses the wide spectrum of communication problems and techniques that invariably occur among social groups with different educational, socioeconomic, racial, and religious origins. It strives to understand how people from other countries and cultures behave, communicate, and perceive the world in this way. Intercultural communication aims to respect and acknowledge people from various cultural origins. Biculturalism or multiculturalism is the consequence of mutual adaptation between two or more diverse cultures as opposed to total assimilation. It allows for sympathetic understanding between distinct cultures and encourages the development of cultural sensitivity.

In international business, a lack of understanding of cultural differences can have serious consequences. Last-minute redesigns and reprints can be very expensive, so it's important to ensure that all text and images you use are culturally appropriate. It's no surprise that cross-cultural understanding and communication are top priorities for today's international companies. We are looking for people with cross-cultural communication skills. But what is intercultural communication?

Intercultural communication examines communication between different cultures and social groups and describes many communication processes and related issues between groups of people from different cultural backgrounds.

Mastering a foreign language is only part of the package. Understanding the other person's cultural background, values, and beliefs also requires understanding. Intercultural communication skills are essential here. They are necessary for successfully communicating with people from other cultures and social groups. Intercultural communication skills also include a willingness to adapt and accept that other cultures may communicate and do things differently.

How would you define intercultural communication?

How can intercultural communication be defined? Intercultural communication means communication that transcends the boundaries of essentially different cultures. Intercultural communication occurs when two or more people from different cultural backgrounds interact

and communicate with each other or with each other. Intercultural communication can therefore be defined as sharing information with different levels of consciousness among people from different cultural backgrounds. Influenced individuals from different cultural groups negotiate common meanings in their interactions. You may have heard the term "intercultural communication". This section presents some commonly accepted academic and applied definitions to clarify this concept and process. It helps scholars and practitioners clarify the meaning of certain terms. The term "intercultural communication" describes a broad range of ideas that are difficult to articulate in one direction. Intercultural communication refers to communication between people of different cultures. (Chen and Starosta, 1998: 28) Intercultural communication is the symbolic, interpretive, transactional, and contextual process by which people of different cultures generate common meaning. (Funny & Köster, 2007: 46) Intercultural communication describes the effects on communicative behavior when different cultures interact with each other. Intercultural communication can therefore be viewed as communication that unfolds in a symbolic intercultural space. (Alasaratnam, 2013: 48) The concept of knowing how to communicate with people from different parts of the world is called intercultural communication. People are able to comprehend how certain norms are prevalent in adjusting to new cultures by comprehending the theories. Theories are used within groups of people in intercultural communication to create a sense of cultural diversity. This is done in the hope that people will be able to discover new things about other cultures. People gain a better understanding of when it is appropriate to behave in situations without disrespecting the people who live in these cultures thanks to the theories that are used; It also broadens their perspective on how intercultural communication can help achieve cultural diversity. In the field of intercultural business communication, a lot of people argue that culture influences how messages are encoded, the medium through which they are transmitted, and how messages are interpreted. Intercultural communication studies interactions between people from different cultural backgrounds. Intercultural communication focuses on social characteristics, thought patterns, and the cultures of various groups of people in addition to language. Understanding the languages, customs, and cultures of people from other countries is also necessary. Cultural agility is a term that is currently used to design a complex set of competencies required for an individual or organization to perform successfully in cross-cultural situations. Intercultural communication plays a role in the social sciences like anthropology, cultural studies, linguistics, psychology, and communication studies. Learning the tools to facilitate cross-cultural interaction is the subject of cultural agility. The foundation for international businesses is also referred to as intercultural communication. Intercultural communication skills are developed by a number of cross-cultural service providers. Intercultural communication is defined as "interaction with speakers of other languages on equal terms and respecting their identities." Identity and culture are also studied within the discipline of communication to analyze how globalization influences ways of thinking, beliefs, values, and identity within and between cultural environments. Research is a major component of the development of intercultural communication skills. Scholars of intercultural communication approach theory with a fluid perspective and deny that cultures can be measured or share universal characteristics. Researchers recognize that culture and correspondence shift alongside cultural changes and speculations ought to consider the consistent moving and

subtleties of society. The investigation of intercultural correspondence requires intercultural understanding. The capacity to appreciate and comprehend cultural differences is intercultural understanding. Language is one example of a significant cultural aspect that is connected to understanding other cultures.

Intercultural communication scholars emphasize that globalization emerged from the increasing diversity of cultures throughout the world and thrives when cultural barriers are removed. The concept of nationality, or the construction of national space, is understood to emerge dialectically through communication and globalization. Globalization plays a central role in the theory of mass communication, media, and cultural communication studies.

Kathryn Sorrells, Ph.D.'s Intercultural Praxis Model teaches us how to deal with the complexities of power differences and cultural differences. This model will assist you with understanding your identity as an individual, and how you can all the more likely speak with others that might be not the same as you. To keep living in a globalized society one can utilize this Praxis model to figure out social contrasts (in light of race, identity, orientation, class, sexual direction, religion, ethnicity, and so forth.) within the historical and institutional structures of power. The Intercultural Communication Praxis Model asks us to be as open as possible when responding to someone whose culture is different from ours. Both our perceptions of ourselves and other cultures are influenced by the media. We learn how to communicate with others and educate ourselves through Sorrells' Praxis Model. In order to navigate intercultural spaces, Sorrells' process includes inquiry, framing, positioning, dialogue, reflection, and action. The Intercultural Praxis Model's first step is inquiry, which is a general interest in learning about and comprehending people from diverse cultural backgrounds and worldviews while challenging one's own perceptions. Therefore, framing is the capacity to switch between the micro, meso, and macro frames and the awareness of "local and global contexts that shape intercultural interactions". Positioning is the consideration of one's position in relation to other people and the ways in which this position may influence one's worldview as well as particular privileges. The turning point in the process is dialogue, during which one gains a deeper comprehension of differences and potential conflicts through interaction with cultures other than one's own. Next, through introspection, reflection teaches one about the values of those differences and enables one to act "in meaningful, effective, and responsible ways" in the world. " This at last prompts activity, which plans to make a more cognizant world by pursuing civil rights and harmony among various societies. Sorrells argues that "intercultural praxis... offers us a process of critical, reflective thinking and acting that enables us to navigate... intercultural spaces we inhabit interpersonally, communally, and globally" in the context of globalization. "

Being successful in an international setting requires understanding cultural implications because culture has a significant influence on how people conduct business. Lack of intercultural sensitivity can alienate employees who work in other countries and have a negative impact on a company's bottom line. It can also offend current or potential customers. To increase cross-cultural connections and intercultural communication abilities, which will increase personal marketability, specific initiatives can be performed.

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